

New insights in robotic colorectal surgery: are we moving to the future or are we stuck in the progress?

Nuevos conocimientos en cirugía colorrectal robótica: ¿vamos hacia el futuro o estamos estancados en el progreso?

349

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Abstract

Colorectal diseases represent a significant burden in modern medicine, with a severe impact on patients' quality of life.

This has driven the need for effective treatments and the refinement of currently available methods. Surgical intervention remains the gold standard for most colorectal conditions. However, because of the complexity of such surgeries, the steep learning curves for surgeons, operator-associated complications, and many other factors, the availability of highly specialized colorectal surgeons does not meet the growing demand. To optimize patient care, several strategies have been analyzed to address these obstacles, most of which focus on shifting from conventional surgical methods to more novel approaches. Robotic surgery (RS) has been a prominent topic since its introduction and has provided outstand-

ing results in various clinical scenarios. Compared with traditional methods, robotic techniques offer distinct advantages. The enhanced dexterity and range of motion provided by robotic tools are invaluable in the surgical field. Moreover, the magnified view provides more clarity, enabling more precise maneuvers. As surgical practices continue to evolve, minimally invasive methods and robotic techniques are gaining relevance worldwide. In this review, we assess the suitability of robotic methods in colorectal surgeries by comparing their outcomes, associated costs, operator learning curves, intraoperative and postoperative complications, and conversion rates to open surgery in contrast to traditional methods.

Keywords: Robotic surgery, colorectal surgery, colorectal disease, surgical learning, surgical complications.

Las enfermedades colorrectales representan una carga significativa en la medicina moderna, con un impacto severo en la calidad de vida de los pacientes. Esto ha impulsado la necesidad de tratamientos efectivos y el perfeccionamiento de los métodos disponibles actualmente. La intervención quirúrgica sigue siendo el estándar de oro para la mayoría de las afecciones colorrectales. Sin embargo, debido a la complejidad de estas cirugías, las pronunciadas curvas de aprendizaje para los cirujanos, las complicaciones asociadas al operador y muchos otros factores, la disponibilidad de cirujanos colorrectales altamente especializados no satisface la creciente demanda. Para optimizar la atención al paciente, se han analizado varias estrategias para abordar estos obstáculos, la mayoría de las cuales se centran en pasar de los métodos quirúrgicos convencionales a enfoques más novedosos. La cirugía robótica (CR) ha sido un tema destacado desde su introducción y ha brindado resultados sobresalientes en varios escenarios clínicos. En comparación con los métodos tradicionales, las técnicas robóticas ofrecen ventajas distintivas. La mayor destreza y el rango de movimiento proporcionados por las herramientas robóticas son invaluable en el campo quirúrgico. Además, la visión ampliada proporciona mayor claridad, lo que permite maniobras más precisas. A medida que las prácticas quirúrgicas continúan evolucionando, los métodos mínimamente invasivos y las técnicas robóticas están ganando relevancia a nivel mundial. En esta revisión, evaluamos la idoneidad de los métodos robóticos en las cirugías colorrectales comparando sus resultados, costos asociados, curvas de aprendizaje de los operadores, complicaciones intraoperatorias y postoperatorias, y las tasas de conversión a cirugía abierta en contraste con los métodos tradicionales.

Palabras clave: Cirugía robótica, cirugía colorrectal, enfermedad colorrectal, aprendizaje quirúrgico, complicaciones quirúrgicas.

Colorectal diseases represent a significant burden in modern medicine, with a severe impact on patients' quality of life¹. Colorectal cancer (CC) is notorious in this regard, for several reasons. CC was the third leading cause of death in 2019, and the second leading cause of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) for cancer worldwide^{2,3}. The rising prevalence of modifiable risk factors such as smoking, alcohol consumption, sedentary behavior, and obesity, along with increased life expectancy, has led to more widespread CC screening and awareness. This, in turn, has resulted in more incidental diagnoses, further contributing to the overall incidence and prevalence of the disease. Between 1990 and 2019, the number of CC cases more than doubled, with deaths attributable to CC following a similar trend, rising from 500,000 to over 1 million^{4,5}.

The burden of CC and other colorectal diseases, coupled with the need for effective treatments has driven the refinement of currently available methods. Surgical intervention remains the gold standard for most colorectal conditions⁶. However, because of the complexity of such surgeries, the steep learning curves for surgeons, operator-associated complications, and many other factors, the availability of highly specialized colorectal surgeons does not meet the growing demand⁷⁻⁹. To optimize patient care, several strategies have been analyzed to address these obstacles, most of which focus on shifting from conventional surgical methods to more novel approaches.

Robotic surgery (RS) has been a prominent topic since its introduction, and has provided outstanding results in various clinical scenarios. Compared with traditional methods, robotic techniques offer distinct advantages¹⁰. The enhanced dexterity and range of motion provided by robotic tools are invaluable in the surgical field. Moreover, the magnified view provides more clarity, enabling more precise maneuvers. As surgical practices continue to evolve, minimally invasive methods and robotic techniques are gaining relevance worldwide¹¹. In this review, we assess the suitability of robotic methods in colorectal surgeries by comparing their outcomes, associated costs, operator learning curves, intraoperative and postoperative complications, and conversion rates to open surgery in contrast to traditional methods.

ROBOTIC COLORECTAL SURGERY: PROS AND CONS

Colorectal surgery itself is known for its high complexity and long learning curves for surgeons. Previous publications have suggested that the learning curve in laparoscopic colorectal surgery ranges from 30 to 80 cases (7).

For instance, Schlachta et al.¹² reported a learning curve of 30 cases, while Bennet et al.¹³ reported a learning curve of 40 cases in right sigmoid colectomy. Notably, Dincler et al.¹⁴ reported a learning curve of 70 cases for near-perfect competence, and 28 cases for acceptable performance. These high numbers prevail when migrating to other colorectal procedures that may or may not be more difficult. While these numbers might not seem overwhelming, the learning curves for appendectomy, cesarean section, and cholecystectomy range from 10 to 20 cases at most¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

Unfortunately, the learning curve for RS is more demanding than that of laparoscopic surgery (LS), and some studies have shown an even steeper learning curve. However, specifically for RS, the learning process is divided into three phases or checkpoints. While achieving the latest phase, named competence, needs over 70 cases, the preceding ones, termed the learning and mastery phases, require only 13 and 28 cases, respectively¹⁸. Another factor to consider is that most available data regarding the learning of RS do not consider prior laparoscopic experience, since it is required to achieve at least 100 basic and 75 complex cases to be certified as a laparoscopic surgeon, which is in turn required to enter RS programs. Therefore, the learning curves of laparoscopic colorectal surgery and robotic colorectal surgery are more summative than comparative¹⁹.

Moving on to the benefits of RS, colorectal RS has shown a significant reduction in the amount of intraoperative and postoperative complications compared to both open and laparoscopic methods²⁰. The enhanced precision allows for more delicate tissue handling, resulting in reduced blood loss, and fewer injuries to surrounding structures. A meta-analysis comparing robotic against laparoscopic total mesorectal excision found that the estimated blood loss (EBL) in the robotic group was lower than its counterpart, although these findings were not statistically significant²¹. In addition, other studies have found that EBL remains similar or slightly lower in the robotic approach, showing no inferiority in contrast to laparoscopic alternatives^{22,23}.

On the other hand, a propensity score-matched analysis showed significant differences across several postoperative complications at the expense of an overall longer operative time for the robotic group. For instance, postoperative ileus, need for transfusion, wound-site infection, and any complication had significantly lower rates in contrast to the laparoscopic group²⁴. The most frequent postoperative complication in RS is anastomotic leakage, with rates ranging from 5% to 11%. Nevertheless, that is still far better than the estimated 19% for laparoscopic procedures²⁵. However, other studies showed similar postoperative morbidity rates between RS and LS. Remarkably, operative outcomes, morbidity rates, and overall survivability in RS have shown a favorable trend during the last two decades, denoting an evolutive and attractive pattern²⁶.

Since CC is the condition with the most widespread implementation of RS, oncological outcomes also serve as a measure of performance. For instance, Widmar et al.²⁷ reported that the robotic approach in right colon cancer produced a higher lymph node yield compared to other approaches such as open and laparoscopic ($P<0.01$), and a higher lymph node to length of surgical specimen ratio in contrast to open colectomy ($P<0.01$). Furthermore, a recent retrospective study reported that patients who underwent robotic non-metastatic primary colon resection had higher lymph node yield and radicality of mesenteric resection, as well as a higher ratio of clear margins. However, no difference was reported in overall survival or disease-free survival (DFS) in contrast to open or laparoscopic approaches²⁸.

In addition, other authors have reported that DFS in RS groups is at least equal to its counterpart. For instance, Spinoglio et al.²⁹ reported a 77% overall survival at 5 years for the RS group, in contrast to the 7% of the open and laparoscopic group. However, DFS was similar at 85% and 83% for the RS and LS group, respectively. Moreover, Khan et al.^{3,30} analyzed 40 patients who underwent robotic complete mesocolic excision, reporting a 99% DFS at 3 years and 90% overall survival at 3 years. Nevertheless, despite all these data, further implementation of RS lies in the standardization of surgical technique for each procedure. Likewise, in terms of oncological outcomes, no prospective data is available at the time to provide more accurate data through more sophisticated methodology and data analysis.

It is important to remark that these findings are not universal and that there are other complications inherent to the robotic technique such as mechanical failure, lack of maintenance, and operative system-related errors. As stated by Quezada-Diaz et al. RS can be safely performed with favorable short-term and oncological outcomes while addressing some of the limitations of laparoscopy, at the expense of longer operative times and highest costs. Therefore, more optimization is needed to consolidate the robotic approach the better option³¹. Although a good proportion of the evidence supports that RS has fewer complications, long-term studies are needed to verify these trends across diverse populations and different procedures.

Subsequently, a key advantage of RS is its lower conversion rate to open surgery. Conversions, often required due to complications or technical difficulties, lead to longer operative times, increased blood loss, and higher postoperative morbidity. Although some studies have found no difference in conversion rates between RS and LS, most of these have poor methodology, small samples, or are retrospective^{32,33}. Conversely, other studies have found a lower conversion rate for RS, ranging from 0 to 7%, and noting that this parameter is highly influenced by high body mass index, severe adhesions, anatomical variants, and history of previous surgeries. A meta-analysis showed that despite the longer operative

time, RS had a 0% conversion rate, in contrast to 8% for LS for right and left hemicolectomy³⁴. Considering the complications inherent to open conversions, decreasing the number of conversions directly impacts morbidity, associated costs, length-of-stay, and mortality.

On another topic, RS-associated costs and operative times are the most significant disadvantages when compared to both open and laparoscopic approaches. A recent pooled analysis has shown that RS adds between 60 to 90 minutes to operative times, which may be associated with increased morbidity and procedure-related costs³⁵. Nevertheless, reports from highly specialized centers with a high volume of robotic cases have reported similar or even shorter operative times at the cost of more expensive robotic systems like DaVinci® Xi which allows a multi-quadrant approach without the need for re-docking. However, these reports represent a minority in contrast to other centers with lower volumes of robotic cases, less specialized surgeons, and less optimized robotic systems^{36,37}.

In terms of expenses, robotic systems require a significant initial investment, along with ongoing maintenance, repairs, and the use of disposable instruments, as well as training expenses for the surgical team³⁸. Moreover, the overall longer operative times and their associated costs have led to the estimation that robotics may add up to \$3,500 per surgical procedure, adding nearly \$2.5 billion annually to healthcare costs. Interestingly, through national databases, the average increment in costs due to RS was about \$2,000-5000 per procedure in contrast to LS³⁹. However, estimations are likely related to the surgical volume of the analyzed centers. Low-volume centers reported a higher incidence of postoperative complications and longer in-hospital stays, which directly impacts the costs of robotic procedures. Conversely, high-volume centers had an overall better outcome profile, shorter in-hospital stay, and similar or lower morbidity, leading to smaller gaps in costs⁴⁰.

While the initial costs of RS are undeniably high, particularly due to the upfront investment and the frequent need for maintenance and constant training, there might be potential long-term savings that could balance the overall investment. As reported earlier, RS offers lower EBL, lower or at least equal postoperative complications, significantly lower need for open conversion, and decreased rates of readmission. Moreover, pooled information from high-volume centers report lower length-of-stay, decreased admission to intensive care units, and overall better survivability after 5 years⁴⁰. As robotic systems continue to evolve and surgical techniques become more standardized, it is expected that RS-associated postoperative complications will decrease.

Conclusions

RS presents a promising advancement in surgical care, offering a viable alternative to conventional surgical methods. Amongst the benefits, the lower intra- and postoperative complications, as well as the overall better survivability and oncological outcomes are the most relevant protagonists. However, the longer operative times, higher initial costs, and the long-term need for investment in maintenance and training may yield an overall negative balance. Additionally, RS does not come without challenges, the steep learning curves and the high upfront investment are crucial obstacles to the widespread of robotic systems. To date, robotic technology still needs optimization, better standardization of surgical techniques, and more rigorous scientific analysis, including prospective studies, case-control trials, randomized trials, and overall higher-quality data. Ultimately, RS offers a pathway towards the future of minimally invasive procedures, with a potential for better patient outcomes and a better balance for cost-effectiveness. However, as of today RS, remains as the alternative and not the first choice in most scenarios.

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